

High Frequency Breakdown Characteristics of Various Electrode Geometries in Air

*W. G. Dunbar
Consultant
Bellevue, WA*

and

*D. L. Schweickart, J. C. Horwath and L. C. Walko
Air Force Research Laboratory
Wright Patterson AF Base, OH*

ABSTRACT

In airborne and spacecraft electronic applications, minimum weight and volume constraints have always influenced electrical component and cabling designs. Insulation system specifications must include the total operating environment, voltage excursions, current capacity, mechanical integrity and aging. This is true for both power source equipment as well as special purpose electronics such as radar or high power transmitters, where bare or insulated conductors are often used for high frequency signal transmission, as well as power transmission. A brief review of relevant data is presented to exemplify the effects of high frequency content on breakdown voltages in air, for specific electrode configurations. At high frequencies, the spacing between electrodes or conductors becomes a deterministic parameter for the breakdown phenomenon known as multipactor. When

the mean free path of an electron exceeds the order of electrode spacing or relative dimension of the high frequency system, multipactor breakdown may occur, usually at pressures less than 10^{-2} torr. Multipactor is prevalent within or around components of the high frequency system such as the waveguide, antenna, cabling, connectors and switches. Information that may be useful to designers of components and interconnections will include high frequency initiation phenomena and multipactor breakdown characteristics. Data concerning low pressure corona initiation on antennae will also be presented.

I. BACKGROUND OF HIGH FREQUENCY BREAKDOWN

High frequency breakdown was of concern as early as 1929 when Ruekema [1] reported that the breakdown in air at room ambient pressure, between 6.25 cm diameter spheres, spaced 2.5 centimeters apart had

Table 1. Frequency and Electrode Related Breakdown Voltages

Frequency [kHz]	Voltage [%]	Electrode Spacing [cm]	Electrode Configuration	Investigator
370	54	3	Point/plane	Misere [2]
370	30	25	Point/plane	Misere [2]
0.06-110	100	0.45	Spheres/plates	Muller [3]
0.06-995	100	0.09	Spheres/plates	Muller [3]

the same breakdown characteristic from 60 Hz to 20 kHz. There was a progressive lowering of the breakdown voltage as the frequency increased from 20 kHz to 60 kHz. This trend continued out to a frequency of 425 kHz, where the breakdown voltage was down to 85% of its low frequency value. (NOTE: In this paper, breakdown voltages expressed in % are based on the 50 to 60 Hz breakdown voltage, for a parallel plate gap at atmospheric pressure, as the 100% value.) Other early (1930's) European investigators extended the frequency range for several electrode configurations, as shown in Table 1.

The data in Table 1 are for atmospheric pressure air. For other pure gases and gas mixtures, the breakdown voltage is a function of gas characteristics.

An additional finding by Pim [4] for the breakdown of air at 200 Mhz, between parallel plates spaced 0.005 cm to 0.09 cm apart, at several pressures, is shown in Figure 1. In this example, the breakdown characteristic maintains a Paschen-like behavior for spacings below about 0.17 mm. For slightly larger gaps, the characteristic is degraded, as the breakdown voltage substantially decreases, due to the secondary electron emission influence. For much larger gaps (> 0.45 mm), the breakdown voltage is pressure dependent, in accordance with the Paschen Law.

Figure 1. Breakdown voltage versus gap width.

Figure 2 [5] shows the breakdown voltage between plates and points at one atmosphere pressure for 0.5 and 1.0 MHz, for spacings greater than 1 cm. These data indicate a significant reduction in breakdown voltage for the higher frequencies. Such data must be considered in the design of high voltage modulator subassemblies.

Figure 2. Breakdown voltage versus spacing, after Misere 1932.

Pfeiffer [6] has completed an excellent literature review of experiments from 1929 through 1991. It includes various high frequency breakdown characteristics with regard to spacing, pressure, electrode geometry, configuration and materials.

II. HIGH FREQUENCY BREAKDOWN VOLTAGE AND MULTIFACTOR

Multipacting breakdown may occur when free electrons are accelerated so that they reach an electrode surface in a half period of the applied rf field. Upon striking the electrode, the electrons produce secondary electrons which are accelerated back across the gap during the next half period, producing more electrons when they strike [7 through 11]. The emission yield of secondary electrons to the incident electrons is greater than 1 when the impact energy is sufficiently high, resulting in a multipacting discharge.

Vance and Nanevicz [7] state, "Although a multipacting breakdown is a resonant phenomenon, it is not required that a unique set of operating conditions occur. There is a wide range of combination of gap spacings, operating frequency, and voltages over which multipacting may be observed. However, there is a lower threshold voltage below which the discharge cannot occur and an upper voltage above which the discharge does not occur. In addition, for a given electrode spacing, there exists a cutoff frequency below which the discharge does not occur. Multipactor discharges can occur over a wide range of frequencies and voltages above the cutoff frequency. Furthermore, in a configuration where more than one path length is available, less frequency selectivity would be experienced." The multipacting breakdown voltage is a function of the product of frequency (Mhz) times spacing (cm). See Figure 3.

Figure 3. Multipacting breakdown voltage as a function of frequency.

Factors influencing multipactor breakdown include the electrode material (metal or dielectric) and its geometry. Multipacting has several deleterious effects that include:

- Localized heating: usually small with negligible damage
- Breakdown: gas released from electrodes results in higher current density,
- Power loss: detuning of the rf circuit and high Q antennae
- Noise and non-linear effects: increased EMI and electron emissions
- Long term erosion of electrode surfaces.

Multipactor may be suppressed by:

- Conformal coating of printed circuits
- Pressurization of critical parts and components
- Encapsulation of electrodes with foam or potting material.

III. ANTENNA EXPERIMENTAL DATA

To determine the high frequency corona initiation of an isolated wire to ground (at infinity), an experimental apparatus was constructed. This geometry is relevant to high power communication antennae designs. Several experiments were conducted using a 4 m long, 0.25 cm diameter wire to simulate this configuration. The high frequency source and corona detection equipment were located on the top surface of a large vacuum chamber (15 m high and 8 m diameter). The wire was suspended from the top of the large vacuum chamber, to maintain a very large chamber to wire diameter ratio. A custom bushing assembly was constructed to transition the applied voltage from outside and extend down 0.6 m inside the vacuum chamber, to mitigate any corona effects from proximity to the chamber wall. The wire "antenna" was energized via a 2.5 cm diameter polytetrafluoroethylene insulated feedthrough, which was incorporated into the bushing design, and extended an additional 0.35 m down into the chamber. Some of the experiments included a 0.3 meter diameter aluminum spheroid simulating an aerodynamic weight attached to the end of the "antenna" wire. The results of the experiments are shown in Figure 4.

These data indicate there is a reduction in the breakdown voltage values between 35 and 45 kHz (as compared to 50 to 60 Hz values) for very small wires in a large vacuum chamber. These data are in agreement with data published by the early investigators [1 through 5] of high frequency breakdown.

Figure 4. Breakdown voltage as a function of frequency.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Parallel plate (pseudo-uniform field) breakdown voltage depends on the electrode diameter, spacing, electrode material and gas. For spacings less than a critical value (typically determined by the excitation frequency) the breakdown voltage will deviate from Paschen-like behavior due to secondary effects. For non-uniform or asymmetrical field geometries associated with antennae, point to ground plane and sharp edges, the breakdown voltage will lower to at least 85% at frequencies above 40 kHz. The actual breakdown voltage % will depend on the complexity of the field. It should be recognized that there is limited breakdown and/or corona data for non-uniform electrodes of various spacing at frequencies above 40 kHz, with the exception of multipactor breakdown which is a separate condition, at very low pressure.

V. REFERENCES

1. I. E. Reukema, Transactions Institute of Electrical Engineering, Vol. 47, 1929, p.38.
2. F. Misere, Arch. Electrotech. Vol. 26. 1932 p.123.
3. Muller, "Der Elektrische Durchschlag von Luft bei Ser hohen Frequenzen," Archiv Fur Elektrotechnik, Vol. 28, 1934, p.341-348.

4. J. A. Pim, Proceedings of IEE, Vol. 96, Part III, 1949, p.117.

5. J. M. Meek and J. D. Craggs, (ed.), Electrical Breakdown of Gases, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1978.

6. W. Pfeiffer, "High-frequency Voltage Stress of Insulation: Methods of Testing," IEEE, Transactions on Electrical Insulation, Vol. 26, No. 2, pp. 239-246, April, 1991.

7. E. F. Vance and J. E. Nanevicz, "Rocket Motor Charging Experiments", Stanford Research Institute Scientific Report 5," SRI Project 4600, Contract AF 19(628)-4800, Stanford Research Institute , Palo Alto, Ca., June, 1966.

8. "Multipactor Breakdown in Space Electronic Systems," Internal Note, IN-ASTR-71-2, Marshall Space Flight Center, AL, March 1971.

9. R. Woo, "Multipacting Breakdown in Coaxial Transmission Lines," Proc. IEEE, April 1968.

10. A. D. McDonald and S. C. Brown, "High Frequency Gas Discharge Breakdown in Helium", Physical Review, Vol. 75, No. 3, pp. 411-418, February 1, 1949.

11. G. August and J. B. Chown, "Reduction of Gas-Discharge Breakdown Thresholds in the Ionosphere Due to Multipacting," Proceedings of the Second Workshop on Voltage Breakdown in Electronic Equipment at Low Pressures, Edited by E. R. Bunker, Jr., JPL, 33-447, p. 193, June, 1970.